

Original Research

Potassium silicate enhances growth in strawberry (*Fragaria* × *ananassa* cv. ‘Camarosa’) by improving anatomical structure

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Abstract

Plant structure is closely linked to its physiological function, where any structural modification can significantly affect plant growth and development. Potassium silicate, a silicon source known to improve plant structural and physiological traits, was applied to strawberry plants (*Fragaria* × *ananassa* cv. ‘Camarosa’) under greenhouse conditions, at different concentrations (0, 5, 10, and 20 mmol·L⁻¹) to assess its effects on growth and anatomy. The 10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment notably optimized key growth parameters, particularly leaf number, alongside anatomical improvements such as increased cuticle and palisade parenchyma thickness, vascular tissue development, including larger midrib and root stele areas, expanded metaxylem diameters and a shift in root stele type from triarch to pentarch. A strong positive correlation was observed between root stele area and leaf number. Remarkably, druse crystals increased by 164%, highlighting their vital role in plant defence. These findings underscore the benefits of moderate potassium silicate concentrations (10 mmol·L⁻¹) in improving root and leaf anatomy, directly enhancing plant growth. It offers practical insights into leveraging silicon-based treatments to optimise crop performance, especially in high-demand crops like strawberries.

Keywords

Leaf, silicon, structural properties, vascular development

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Citation: Kelij, S., Yasaghi, S. (2025). Potassium silicate enhances growth in strawberry (*Fragaria* × *ananassa* cv. ‘Camarosa’) by improving anatomical structure. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (1)

Received: 02.06.2025 / **Accepted:** 17.10.2025 / **Published:** 27.10.2025

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.22944>

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Kalijev silikat spodbuja rast jagod (*Fragaria* × *ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa') z izboljšanjem anatomskih struktur

Izvleček

Struktura rastline je tesno povezana z njeno fiziološko funkcijo, pri čemer lahko vsaka strukturna sprememba znatno vpliva na rast in razvoj rastline. Kalijev silikat, vir silicija, za katerega je znano, da izboljšuje strukturne in fiziološke lastnosti rastlin, je bil v različnih koncentracijah (0, 5, 10 in 20 mmol·L⁻¹) uporabljen na jagodnih rastlinah (*Fragaria* × *ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa') v rastlinjaku, da bi ocenili njegove učinke na rast in anatomijo. Obdelava s 10 mmol·L⁻¹ je znatno optimizirala ključne parametre rasti, zlasti število listov, poleg anatomskih izboljšav, kot so povečana debelina kutikule in palisadnega parenhima, razvoj žilnega tkiva, vključno z večjimi površinami srednje žile in koreninskega stela, povečanimi premeri metaksilema in prehodom iz triarhskega v pentarhski tip koreninske stele. Opazili so močno pozitivno korelacijo med površino koreninske stele in številom listov. Zanimivo je, da so se kristali druse povečali za 164 %, kar poudarja njihovo pomembno vlogo pri zaščiti rastlin. Ti izsledki poudarjajo prednosti zmernih koncentracij kalijevega silikata (10 mmol·L⁻¹) pri izboljšanju anatomije korenin in listov, kar neposredno izboljša rast rastlin. Ponujajo praktične vpogled v izkoriščanje obdelav na osnovi silicija za optimizacijo donosa pridelkov, zlasti pri pridelkih z visokim povpraševanjem, kot so jagode.

Ključne besede

List, silicij, strukturne lastnosti, razvoj prevajalnih elementov

Introduction

Silicon is a key component of soils, and plants absorb it in considerable amounts. It has been a subject of scientific interest for decades, prompting extensive research on the application of silicate materials as fertilisers (Uhlen, 1974). As an integral component of cell walls, silicon not only reinforces structural stability but also actively supports key metabolic and physiological processes. Its significance becomes particularly evident under biotic and abiotic stresses, where it enhances plant resilience (Liang et al., 2006).

The cultivated strawberry (*Fragaria* × *ananassa*), because of its pleasant taste, vitamin richness, and antioxidant properties, has high commercial and economic importance and has attracted significant attention (Giamperi et al., 2012). Providing nutrients over the growth period is essential for increasing the yield and quality of strawberries. Silicon can be classified among these nutrients. The use of Silica-based compounds in agriculture has proven to enhance plant vitality and performance. In different settings, including fields and greenhouses, the influence of silicon-based fertilisers on crop development has been entirely documented (Liang et al., 2015). Several

studies have demonstrated the positive effects of silica on strawberry plants. For instance, Wang and Galleta (1998) reported that the potassium silicate application improved plant growth, increased chlorophyll content, enhanced the composition of unsaturated fatty acids and membrane lipids, and ultimately supported strawberry metabolism. Similarly, Dehghani Poodeh et al. (2015) found that treatments with potassium silicate and nano-silica significantly increased key growth parameters, such as leaf number and leaf formation rate, while also improving reproductive traits, including flowering and fruit firmness. Further research has emphasised the effect of potassium silicate in alleviating environmental stress. Yaghubi et al. (2016) found that potassium silicate not only improved growth and physiological traits in strawberries but also reduced cellular damage under salt stress. Moreover, physiological parameters, including stomatal conductance, chlorophyll content and photosynthesis rate, were enhanced in strawberry plants under water stress by the application of potassium silicate (Avestan et al., 2021).

Plant anatomical characteristics are intricately linked to the functional capabilities of plants, and any structural modifications have the potential to significantly influence physi-

ological processes (Santos et al., 2015). Although numerous studies have examined the effects of silicon on plant development, physiology, flowering, yield, and fruit quality, its role in shaping the anatomical structure of strawberries remains poorly understood. This study seeks to expand fundamental knowledge by investigating how potassium silicate affects both growth and anatomical traits of commercial strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa') under greenhouse conditions. By linking anatomical modifications with growth responses, our findings contribute to basic plant science while also offering insights that may inform future agricultural practices for strawberry cultivation. The subsequent key questions addressed in this study include: (1) How do different concentrations of potassium silicate impact the growth parameters of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'? (2) What exact structural changes are observed in response to potassium silicate application? (3) Can the detected anatomical adaptations be correlated with enhanced growth performance under potassium silicate treatment?

Materials and Methods

Plant cultivation and treatments

Strawberry plants with 3–4 leaves, sourced from Ashian Sabz Emad company (Karaj, Iran), were transplanted into 2.5 kg pots. The soil texture was sandy loam with 51% sand, 38% silt, and 11% clay, with an electrical conductivity (EC) of 0.47 dS/m and a pH value of 7.71. The plants were housed in a greenhouse environment featuring a photoperiod of 14/10 h light/dark, 60 – 70% relative humidity, and temperature ranging from 16 – 18 °C to 21 – 22 °C from November 2023 to February 2024. Two weeks after transplantation, the plants underwent weekly potassium silicate treatment (K_2SiO_3 42%, Sigma) at concentrations of 0, 5, 10, and 20 mmol/L, applied via soil drenching. Throughout the experiment, plants were watered as needed. The potassium silicate applications persisted for a duration of two months

Growth parameters and anatomy

The number of leaves per plant was recorded, and other growth parameters were determined using graph paper. For each treatment, five individual plants (biological replicates) were used. From each plant, five separate samples of root, petiole, and leaf were collected and analysed individually

(technical replicates), totalling 25 replicates per organ per treatment. For anatomical analysis, samples of leaves, petioles, and roots were immediately fixed in a glycerin-alcohol solution. Transverse sections were taken from the central part of the middle leaflet of matured leaves and the median section of the petiole and root, along their longitudinal axis. Using a steel blade. An Olympus CX43 microscope with a digital camera was employed for microscopic analysis, and ImageJ software (version 1.54g) was used for measuring anatomical features. Anatomical terminology follows the standards outlined in Esau's "Plant Anatomy" (Evert, 2006).

Statistical analysis

The SPSS software (version 21) was employed to analyse the obtained data. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to explore the differences among the studied factors across the treatments using Duncan's multiple range test at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. Results are presented as the mean \pm standard error (SE) of five independent replicates. Additionally, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to explore the relationships between anatomical characteristics and growth parameters using SPSS. To highlight the maximum potential effect of the treatments on each trait, we calculated the growth rate of each growth and anatomical trait as the difference between the highest treatment value and the control value, and visualised the results using a sunburst chart. Microsoft Excel (version 2021) was used for the sunburst chart and plotting all the figures.

Results

The leaf number per plant enhanced significantly in 10 mmol·L⁻¹ potassium silicate, while there were no meaningful differences among other treatments. The strawberry plants exposed to 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹ potassium silicate exhibited notable improvement in petiole length. Likewise, leaf width and length increased significantly at 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹ potassium silicate. However, increasing the potassium silicate level to 20 mmol·L⁻¹ didn't show significant enhancement in petiole length and leaf width and length. Potassium silicate application had no significant effects on shoot and root length of strawberry plants, and no considerable difference with the control was observed in any of the treatments (Table 1).

The leaf anatomical structure of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa' (Figure 1A) showed a bifacial leaf. Leaf thickness peaked under 10 mmol·L⁻¹ potassium silicate ($p < 0.05$), and was at 20 mmol·L⁻¹. The thickest upper cuticle was also observed in the 10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment, though no significant differences appeared at other concentrations. Lower cuticle thickness remained unchanged across treatments. The 10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment significantly increased upper epidermis thickness, while lower epidermis thickness showed no significant variation. Palisade and spongy parenchyma

were also thickest at 10 mmol·L⁻¹, with no notable differences among other treatments (Table 2).

In the midrib (Figure 1-B), annular collenchyma and a nearly circular stele were observed. Midrib thickness increased in 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatments but decreased at 20 mmol·L⁻¹. The thickest collenchyma was at 10 mmol·L⁻¹, with no difference between 20 mmol·L⁻¹ and the control. Stele area improved at 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹ and declined at 20 mmol·L⁻¹. The largest metaxylem diameter appeared at 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹, and the smallest at 20 mmol·L⁻¹ (Table 2).

Table 1. Effects of potassium silicate on growth parameters of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'.

Tabela 1. Učinki kalijevega silikata na parametre rasti *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'.

Treatments	Leaf number	Petiole length (Cm)	Leaf width (Cm)	Leaf length (Cm)	Shoot length (Cm)	Root length (Cm)
Control	4.50 ± 0.57 b	6.02 ± 0.47 b	2.82 ± 0.51 b	3.17 ± 0.34 b	16.62 ± 0.94 a	14.3 ± 2.4 a
5 mmol·L ⁻¹	5.25 ± 0.5 b	7.66 ± 0.86 a	3.56 ± 0.33 a	3.83 ± 0.3 a	15.62 ± 0.94 a	13.37 ± 1.4 a
10 mmol·L ⁻¹	6.50 ± 0.57 a	7.48 ± 0.61 a	3.63 ± 0.28 a	3.73 ± 0.34 a	16.12 ± 4.1 a	13.5 ± 3 a
20 mmol·L ⁻¹	5.25 ± 0.5 b	5.97 ± 0.61 b	2.93 ± 0.3 b	3.07 ± 0.26 b	15.12 ± 2.8 a	13 ± 3.7 a

Note: Data represent mean ± SE of five independent replicates. Means followed by the same letters within each column are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$

Figure 1. Leaf cross-section of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa', and displaying different measurement parameters. A, Leaf blade (10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment, for example); UCT: upper cuticle thickness, UET: upper epidermis thickness, PPT: Palisade parenchyma thickness, SPT: Spongy parenchyma thickness, LET: lower epidermis thickness, LCT: lower cuticle thickness, LT: leaf thickness. B, Leaf midrib (5 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment, for example); MT: midrib thickness, CoT: collenchyma thickness, StA: stele area, MD: metaxylem diameter.

Slika 1. Prez list *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa' in prikaz različnih merilnih parametrov. A, listna ploščica (na primer obdelava z 10 mmol·L⁻¹); UCT: debelina zgornje kutikule, UET: debelina zgornje epiderme, PPT: debelina palisadnega parenhima, SPT: debelina spongioznega parenhima, LET: debelina spodnje epiderme, LCT: debelina spodnje kutikule, LT: debelina lista. B, srednja žila lista (na primer obdelava s 5 mmol·L⁻¹); MT: debelina srednje žile, CoT: debelina kolenhimata, StA: površina stele, MD: premer metaksilema.

In petiole anatomy (Figure 2-A), collenchyma beneath the epidermis, two small steles, a large central stele, and druse crystals were observed. Petiole and collenchyma thickness increased only at 10 mmol·L⁻¹, with no significant difference from 5 mmol·L⁻¹. Central stele dimensions and smaller stele areas showed no significant change across treatments. Druse crystals increased in all potassium silicate treatments compared to the control, but differences among 5, 10, and 20 mmol·L⁻¹ were not significant (Table 2).

In root anatomy (Figure 2-B), exodermis, cortex, endodermis, pericycle, and vascular bundles were identified. Potassium silicate significantly increased root cross-sectional area and cortex thickness, both of which were highest at 10 mmol·L⁻¹ and lowest in the control. Exodermis thickness showed no significant difference among treatments (Table 2). Root stele area followed the same trend as root cross-section area, highest at 10 mmol·L⁻¹ and lowest in the control. Metaxylem thickness increased significantly in 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatments compared to 20 mmol·L⁻¹ and control. Xylem rows varied from 3 to 5, corresponding to triarch to pentarch stele types. Xylem rows peaked at

10 mmol·L⁻¹ (4.75 ± 5 , indicating pentarch), while the control showed the lowest number (3.25 ± 5 , indicating triarch) (Table 2, Figure 3).

Pearson correlation analysis indicated that a notable positive association exists between root and leaf growth and anatomy with vascular tissue development (Figure 4). As follows, there was a significant correlation between the root stele area and leaf number ($r = 0.82^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), the midrib collenchyma thickness and root metaxylem diameter ($r = 0.73^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), leaf length and midrib stele area ($r = 0.8^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), and also, palisade parenchyma thickness and midrib metaxylem diameter ($r = 0.79^{**}$, $p < 0.01$).

The sunburst chart (Figure 5) shows that potassium silicate significantly affected strawberry growth and anatomy. Leaf number had the highest growth increase (44%), followed by petiole traits and leaf width. Root anatomy, especially root cross-sectional area, rose by 158%. In leaves, midrib metaxylem diameter increased by 91%, indicating improved vascular development. Petiole druse crystal number showed the strongest anatomical response with a 164% increase.

Figure 2. Petiole and root cross sections of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa', and displaying different measurement parameters. A, Petiole (5 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment, for example); PD: petiole diameter, CoT: collenchyma thickness, DC: druse crystal, MaD: major diameter of the largest stele, MiD: minor diameter of the largest stele, StA: stele area. B, Root (10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment, for example); CT: cortex thickness, EXT: exoderm thickness, Xy: xylem, StA: stele area, MD: metaxylem diameter.

Slika 2. Prerez listnega peclja in korenine *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. „Camarosa“ z različnimi merilnimi parametri. A, listni peclj (na primer obdelava s 5 mmol·L⁻¹); PD: premer listnega peclja, CoT: debelina kolenhimata, DC: druse kristal, MaD: glavni premer največjega stela, MiD: stranski premer največjega stela, StA: površina stela. B, Korenina (na primer obdelava z 10 mmol·L⁻¹); CT: debelina skorje, EXT: debelina ekso-derm, Xy: ksilem, StA: površina stela, MD: premer metaksilema.

Figure 3. Root stele type of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'. A: Triarch stele, B: Tetrarch stele, C: Pantarch stele. En: endoderm, Pr: pericycle, Xy: xylem, Ph: phloem.

Slika 3. Root stele type of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'. A: Triarch stele, B: Tetrarch stele, C: Pantarch stele. En: endoderm, Pr: pericycle, Xy: xylem, Ph: phloem.

Table 2. Effects of potassium silicate on the anatomical characteristics of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'.

Tabela 2. Učinki kalijevega silikata na anatomske značilnosti *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'

Anatomical characteristics	Control	5 mmol·L ⁻¹	10 mmol·L ⁻¹	20 mmol·L ⁻¹
Leaf thickness(µm)	178 ± 9.2 c	213 ± 8.4 b	264 ± 15.2 a	166 ± 8.6 c
upper cuticle thickness(µm)	7.29 ± 0.87 b	6.4 ± 0.45 b	10.15 ± 1.5 a	7.88 ± 0.36 b
lower cuticle thickness(µm)	5 ± 1.4 a	5.05 ± 2 a	4.85 ± 1.6 a	4.74 ± 1.5 a
upper epidermis thickness(µm)	21.7 ± 2.7 b	22 ± 1.7 b	27.1 ± 1.5 a	21.9 ± 1.1 b
Lower epidermis thickness(µm)	14.2 ± 3.5 a	14.7 ± 1.5 a	15.2 ± 4 a	15.6 ± 2.3 a
Palisade parenchyma thickness(µm)	54.3 ± 7.8 b	64.2 ± 6.1 b	79.2 ± 5.2 a	55 ± 7.4 b
Spongy parenchyma thickness(µm)	78.7 ± 5.6 b	89.8 ± 7 b	106.2 ± 16.9 a	84.5 ± 13 b
Midrib thickness(µm)	366 ± 13.7 b	443 ± 37.6 a	430 ± 22 a	307 ± 39 c
Midrib collenchyma thickness(µm)	49.45 ± 3.9 c	69.75 ± 6.1 b	80.98 ± 6.3 a	44.96 ± 8.7 c
Midrib stele area(µm ²)	12009 ± 1370 b	18996 ± 5603 a	17640 ± 934 a	9717 ± 2027 b
Midrib metaxylem diameter(µm)	6.48 ± 0.72 b	11.1 ± 1 a	12.4 ± 1.8 a	7.88 ± 1.4 b
Petiole thickness(µm)	1802 ± 50.4 b	1832 ± 105 b	2104 ± 196 a	1744 ± 36.9 b
Petiole collenchyma thickness(µm)	35.7 ± 9.7 b	41 ± 8.7 ab	51.7 ± 3.4 a	32 ± 7.9 b
Major diameter of central vessel(µm)	743 ± 86 ab	650 ± 29 b	758 ± 55 a	690 ± 61 ab
Minor diameter of central vessel(µm)	427 ± 71 b	434 ± 16 ab	510 ± 47 a	442 ± 42 ab
Small stele area(µm ²)	63102 ± 20331 a	68704 ± 5494 a	54408 ± 9045 a	56090 ± 4523 a
Number of druse crystals	5.2 ± 2.9 b	12 ± 3.16 a	12.5 ± 2.08 a	13.75 ± 2.75 a
Root cross section area(µm ²)	651k ± 79k c	1514k ± 156k ab	1683k ± 116k a	1335k ± 126k b
Root cortex thickness(µm)	306 ± 48 c	482 ± 18 b	614 ± 31 a	504 ± 47 b
Root exoderm thickness(µm)	33.7 ± 14 a	35.7 ± 13 a	45.6 ± 12 a	44.8 ± 16 a
Root stele area (µm ²)	42331 ± 10588 c	61113 ± 4333 b	79591 ± 5769 a	71349 ± 10692 ab
Root metaxylem diameter(µm)	12.6 ± 1.6 b	18.9 ± 1.29 a	17.2 ± 0.86 a	14 ± 2.2 b
Number of xylem rows	3.25 ± 0.5 c	3.75 ± 0.5 b c	4.75 ± 0.5 a	4.25 ± 0.5 ab

Note: Data represent mean ± SE of five independent replicates. Means followed by the same letters within each column are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 4. Pearson correlation between growth parameters and anatomical traits; LT: leaf thickness, UET: upper Epidermis thickness, LET: lower epidermis thickness, PaT: palisade thickness, SpT: spongy thickness, MT: midrib thickness, CoT: collenchyma thickness, MSA: midrib stele area, PT: petiole thickness, PCoT: petiole collenchyma thickness, MaD: metaxylem diameter, SSA: small stele area, DN: druse crystal number, RA: root area, RCT: root cortex thickness, RET: root exoderm thickness, RSA: root stele area, RMD: root metaxylem diameter, RSXN: root stele xylem number, LN: leaf number, PL: petiole length, Lw: leaf width, LL: leaf length, RL: root length, ShL: shoot length.

Slika 4. Pearsonova korelacija med parametri rasti in anatomskimi značilnostmi; LT: debelina lista, UET: debelina zgornje epiderme, LET: debelina spodnje epiderme, PaT: debelina palisade, SpT: debelina spongije, MT: debelina srednje žile, CoT: debelina kolenhim, MSA: površina srednje žile, PT: debelina peclja, PCoT: debelina kolenhimusa peclja, MaD: premer metaksilema, SSA: površina majhne stele, DN: število drusnih kristalov, RA: površina korenine, RCT: debelina skorje korenine, RET: debelina eksoderma korenine, RSA: površina stele korenine, RMD: premer metaksilema korenine, RSXN: število ksilema stele korenine, LN: število listov, PL: dolžina peclja, Lw: širina lista, LL: dolžina lista, RL: dolžina korenine, ShL: dolžina poganjka.

Figure 5. The sunburst chart illustrates which anatomical characteristics and growth parameters were most affected by the potassium silicate treatment.

Slika 5. Tortni diagram prikazuje, katere anatomsko značilnosti in parametri rasti so bili najbolj prizadeti zaradi obdelave s kalijevim silikatom.

Discussion

The application of potassium silicate (K_2SiO_3) significantly enhanced strawberry leaf growth by improving leaf traits, which form the main part of the vegetative body. The finding that the $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ potassium silicate treatment produced more leaves than the $20\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ treatment suggests that there is an optimal concentration for stimulating strawberry leaf development. Excessive application may disturb ionic balance or create osmotic stress, which can limit leaf expansion and overall growth. Similar results were reported by Dehghani Poodeh et al. (2015), who found that $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ K_2SiO_3 enhanced strawberry growth while higher doses ($15\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) reduced leaf number. Likewise, Mavrič Cermelj et al. (2022) observed diminishing returns at higher silicon concentrations in barley, attributed to nutrient antagonisms. These findings indicate that moderate doses of potassium silicate are more effective for leaf formation than supra-optimal concentrations. Our study found a significant increase in petiole length at 5 and $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ K_2SiO_3 , contrasting with findings by Wang and Galleta (1998) and Dehghani Poodeh et al. (2015), who reported a decrease under Si treatments. Tabatabaei (2016) showed a 37% increase in strawberry leaf area with silica under salinity stress, supporting our results on enhanced leaf length and width. Although leaf growth improved at $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, shoot and root lengths showed no significant change, consistent with Munns and Tester (2008), who found no effect on root length under non-saline conditions. This effect can be attributed to the fact that potassium silicate influenced the architecture and structural characteristics of the roots rather than their elongation. As demonstrated by the anatomical results in the present study, root cross-sectional area, thickness of cortex, the number of vascular bundles, stele area, and the metaxylem elements diameter all increased under the treatment. These findings align with those of Rachmawati et al. (2021), who reported similar anatomical increments in rice roots following potassium silicate application.

The results emphasise the concentration-dependent impact of potassium silicate on leaf anatomy, with $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ showing the greatest improvements in traits like overall leaf thickness, upper cuticle, upper epidermis, and mesophyll layers. Supporting this, Asmar et al. (2013) found that silicon uptake improves chlorophyll levels, photosynthesis, and leaf thickness in strawberry. In contrast, $20\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ led to declines in most anatomical traits, suggesting possible toxicity, consistent with findings by Azab

et al. (2022). No notable changes were observed in the lower cuticle and epidermis. Genetic and developmental programs differ between adaxial and abaxial epidermis, leading to inherent differences in their anatomical characteristics and responsiveness (Nakata & Okada, 2013). More generally, as Borowski and Michałek (2009) noted, factors such as species, application method, and light intensity can influence anatomical responses to fertilisation.

Potassium silicate application led to increased midrib thickness, along with greater collenchyma development, stele area, and metaxylem diameter. Similarly, Bijanzadeh et al. (2022) observed that sodium silicate reduced midrib area loss in drought-stressed maize and enhanced xylem element diameters under various conditions. These changes suggest improved vascular development, as noted by Aguraijuja et al. (2015), who linked larger stele areas to better water and nutrient transport. Zhang et al. (2023) also associated larger xylem vessels with enhanced hydraulic conductivity. In contrast, the reduced metaxylem diameter at $20\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ may indicate impaired water transport (Qaderi et al., 2019). The significant increase in midrib collenchyma thickness highlights its role in providing cell wall reinforcement and, consequently, mechanical strength to the leaf (Leroux 2012).

Potassium silicate, particularly at $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, significantly increased petiole and collenchyma thickness by enhancing the number of collenchyma layers, thus improving leaf structural support. Bokor et al. (2019) found that while silicon did not alter petiole structure in *Phoenix dactylifera*, it reinforced sclerenchyma tissues and promoted lignification, highlighting silicon's role in strengthening supportive tissues. Additionally, all potassium silicate treatments increased druse crystal formation, likely due to potassium's role in releasing calcium, which then binds with oxalic acid to form calcium oxalate crystals. Calcium oxalate crystal formation is a recognised mechanism for regulating calcium levels (Kelij et al, 2025). However, no significant changes were observed in the dimensions or area of the petiole stele, suggesting potassium silicate's effects are tissue-specific.

The variation in xylem row numbers, shifting from triarch to pentarch types, reflects vascular flexibility that may enhance water and nutrient uptake. The highest number of xylem rows at $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ potassium silicate, along with increased stele area and metaxylem thickness at 5 and $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, indicates improved vascular efficiency. Vaculík et al. (2012) also reported that silicon mitigated cadmi-

um's negative effects on vascular development in maize. Potassium silicate at 10 mmol·L⁻¹ significantly increased root cross-sectional area and cortex thickness, suggesting enhanced root growth due to better nutrient uptake. Similarly, silicon improved root length and thickness in soybean (Chung et al., 2020) and promoted root development in *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* under stress (Zhang et al., 2018). Meanwhile, the exodermis thickness remained unchanged, indicating its consistent protective role across treatments.

Pearson correlation analysis revealed that increased leaf thickness under potassium silicate treatment is mainly due to greater collenchyma and palisade parenchyma thickness. Similarly, root diameter increased primarily through cortex thickening, followed by stele expansion. The strong correlations between root and leaf anatomical traits indicate that enhanced root structure contributes significantly to improved leaf growth. Potassium silicate also enhanced vascular tissue development, improving water and nutrient transport and enabling more efficient water regulation, which is especially important for strawberry plants with high water demand and limited root systems (Elmakarem & Mostafa, 2025).

Enhanced midrib vascular development and increased metaxylem diameter further supported leaf expansion and growth. This aligns with Ma and Yamaji (2006), who reported that silicon boosts cell elongation by improving cell wall extensibility, thereby strengthening the vascular system and its overall function.

Specifically, leaf and root tissues respond to environmental changes (Ky et al., 2024). In this study, the sunburst chart analysis shows that potassium silicate primarily prioritises the increase in energy-producing units, such as leaves, over other growth parameters. It also demonstrates that the effect of this treatment is more pronounced on vascular elements rather than supporting tissues like collenchyma. In fact, silicon enhances vascular elements, contributing to both greater structural strength and improved water and mineral transport. Additionally, the significant increase in druse crystals highlights its role in establishing an important defensive strategy.

Conclusions

This study highlights the concentration-dependent positive effects of potassium silicate (K₂SiO₃) on strawberry growth and anatomy under non-stress conditions. The optimal 10 mmol·L⁻¹ concentration improved leaf and root traits, increased leaf number and thickness, and enhanced vascular function. Silicon was shown to strengthen mechanical tissues like collenchyma, promote vascular development, and support defensive structures such as druse crystals, boosting plant resilience and productivity. The findings support the use of silica-based fertilisers in strawberry cultivation, with further research needed on silicon's interaction with environmental factors for sustainable agriculture.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, S.K; investigation, S.K and S.Y; Data curation, S.K and S.Y; writing and editing, S.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgement

We thank Mr. Majid Harati and Mr. Abdolreza Yadollahpour for their insightful comments and guidance during the project.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17454640>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Aguraijuja, K., Klóšeiko, J., Ots, K., & Lukjanova, A. (2015). Effect of wood ash on leaf and shoot anatomy, photosynthesis and carbohydrate concentrations in birch on a cutaway peatland. *Environmental monitoring and assessment*, 187(7), 444.
- Asmar, S. A., Castro, E., Pasqual, M., Pereira, F., & Dória, J. (2013). Changes in leaf anatomy and photosynthesis of micropropagated banana plantlets under different silicon sources. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 161, 328–332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2013.07.021>
- Avestan, S., Ghasemnezhad, M., Esfahani, M., & Barker, A. (2021). Effects of nanosilicon dioxide on leaf anatomy, chlorophyll fluorescence, and mineral element composition of strawberry under salinity stress. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 44(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904167.2021.1936036>
- Azab, E. S., Alshallash, K. S., Alqahtani, M. M., Safhi, F. A., Alshamrani, S. M., Ali, M. A. M., & El-Taher, A. M. (2022). Physiological, anatomical, and agronomic responses of *Cucurbita pepo* to exogenously sprayed potassium silicate at different concentrations under varying water regimes. *Agronomy*, 12(9), 2155. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12092155>
- Bijanazadeh, E., Barati, V., & Egan, T. P. (2022). Foliar application of sodium silicate mitigates drought-stressed leaf structure in corn (*Zea mays* L.). *South African Journal of Botany*, 147, 8–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2021.12.032>
- Bokor, B., Soukup, M., Vaculík, M., Vd'ačný, P., Weidinger, M., Lichtscheidl, I., & Lux, A. (2019). Silicon uptake and localization in date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*) – A unique association with sclerenchyma. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 10, 988. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2019.00988>
- Borowski, E., & Michałek, S. (2009). The effect of placement and light conditions during foliar application of Insole U fertilizer on gas exchange, yield, and the quality of spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.). *Folia Horticulturae*, 21, 61–71. <https://doi.org/10.2478/fhort-2013-0126>
- Chung, Y. S., Lee, U., Heo, S., Silva, R. R., Na, C.-I., & Kim, Y. (2020). Image-based machine learning characterizes root nodule in soybean exposed to silicon. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 11, 520161. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.520161>
- Dehghani Poodeh, S., Ghobadi, C., Baninasab, B., Gheysari, M., & Bidabadi, S. S. (2015). Effects of potassium silicate and nanosilica on quantitative and qualitative characteristics of a commercial strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'). *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 39, 502–507. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904167.2015.1086789>
- Dehghani Poodeh, S., Ghobadi, C., Baninasab, B., Gheysari, M., & Shiranibidabadi, S. (2018). Effect of silicon on growth and development of strawberry under water deficit conditions. *Horticultural Plant Journal*, 4, 226–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hpj.2018.09.004>
- Elmakarem, A. A. A., & Mostafa, N. A. (2025). The effect of potassium silicate on the productivity and storability of spinach plants (*Spinacia oleracea* L.). *Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences*, 24, 38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44447-025-00038-3>
- Evert, R. F. (2006). *Esau's plant anatomy: Meristems, cells, and tissues of the plant body: Their structure, function, and development* (3rd ed.). John Wiley & Sons. <https://doi.org/10.1002/0470047380>
- Giampieri, F., Tulipani, S., Alvarez-Suarez, J. M., Quiles, J. L., Mezzetti, B., & Battino, M. (2012). The strawberry: Composition, nutritional quality, and impact on human health. *Nutrition*, 28, 9–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nut.2011.08.009>
- Hancock, J. F., Lavín, A., & Retamales, J. B. (1999). Our southern strawberry heritage: *Fragaria chiloensis* of Chile. *HortScience*, 34(5), 814–816. <https://doi.org/10.21273/HORTSCI.34.5.814>
- Kelij, S., Hosseinzadeh, Z., & Rezapour, A. (2025). Evaluating anatomical and biochemical responses to cement dust pollution in *Quercus castaneifolia* C.A. Mey. and *Zelkova carpinifolia* (Pall.). *iForest*, 18, 102–108. <https://doi.org/10.3832/IFOR4574-018>
- Ky, A. R. F., Konaté, M. L., & Kouamé, N. F. (2024). Impact of water deficit on the anatomical structure of more productive and less productive cashew trees (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) in Côte d'Ivoire. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 68(1), 52–68.
- Leroux, O. (2012). Collenchyma: A versatile mechanical tissue with dynamic cell walls. *Annals of Botany*, 110, 1083–1098. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcs186>
- Liang, Y., Nikolic, M., Bélanger, R., Gong, H., & Song, A. (2015). Effect of silicon on crop growth, yield, and quality. In *Silicon in agriculture: From theory to practice* (pp. 209–223).
- Liang, Y., Zhang, W., Chen, Q., Liu, Y., & Ding, R. (2006). Effect of exogenous silicon (Si) on H⁺-ATPase activity, phospholipids, and fluidity of plasma membrane in leaves of salt-stressed barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 57, 212–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envexpbot.2005.05.012>
- Ma, J. F., & Yamaji, N. (2006). Silicon uptake and accumulation in higher plants. *Trends in Plant Science*, 11, 392–397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2006.06.007>
- Mavrič Čermelj, A., Fideršek, E., Golob, A., Kacjan Maršič, N., Vogel Mikuš, K., & Germ, M. (2022). Different concentrations of potassium silicate in nutrient solution affect selected growth characteristics and mineral composition of barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). *Plants*, 11(11), 1405. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11111405>
- Munns, R., & Tester, M. (2008). Mechanisms of salinity tolerance. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 59, 651–681. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.arplant.59.032607.092911>
- Nakata, M., & Okada, K. (2013). The leaf adaxial–abaxial boundary and lamina growth. *Plants*, 2(2), 174–202. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants2020174>
- Qaderi, M. M., Martel, A. B., & Dixon, S. L. (2019). Environmental factors influence plant vascular system and water regulation. *Plants*, 8(3), 65. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants8030065>
- Rachmawati, D., Ramadhani, A. N., & Fatikhasari, Z. (2021). The effect of silicate fertilizer on the root development of rice and its tolerance to salinity stress. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 724, 012004.
- Santos, K. R., Pereira, M. P., Ferreira, A. C. G., Rodrigues, L., Castro, E., Corrêa, F., & Pereira, F. (2015). *Typha domingensis* Pers. growth responses to leaf anatomy and photosynthesis as influenced by phosphorus. *Aquatic Botany*, 122, 47–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquabot.2015.01.007>

- Tabatabaei, S. J. (2016). Interactive effects of Si and NaCl on growth, yield, photosynthesis, and ion content in strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa* var. Camarosa). *Journal of Plant Nutrition* 39(11), 1524-1535. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904167.2016.1161771>
- Uhlen, G. (1974). The effect of calcium silicate in barley pot experiments. *Agricultural and Food Science*, 46, 296–306. <https://doi.org/10.23986/afsci.71887>
- Vaculík, M., Landberg, T., Greger, M., Luxová, M., Stolaríková, M., & Lux, A. (2012). Silicon modifies root anatomy, and uptake and subcellular distribution of cadmium in young maize plants. *Annals of Botany*, 110, 433–443. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcs039>
- Wang, S. Y., & Galletta, G. J. (1998). Foliar application of potassium silicate induces metabolic changes in strawberry plants. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 21, 157–167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904169809365390>
- Yaghubi, K., Ghaderi, N., Vafaei, Y., & Javadi, T. (2016). Potassium silicate alleviates deleterious effects of salinity on two strawberry cultivars grown under soilless pot culture. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 213, 87–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2016.10.012>
- Zhang, Y., Ding, C., Liu, Y., Li, S., Li, X., Xi, B., & Duan, J. (2023). Xylem anatomical and hydraulic traits vary within crown but do not respond to water and nitrogen addition in *Populus tomentosa*. *Agricultural Water Management*, 278, 108169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2023.108169>
- Zhang, W., Yu, X., Li, M., Lang, D., Zhang, X., & Xie, Z. (2018). Silicon promotes growth and root yield of *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* under salt and drought stresses through enhancing osmotic adjustment and regulating antioxidant metabolism. *Crop Protection*, 107, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10265-017-0927-3>